

Effect of growth location on protein content of rice cultivar L202.

Sample	% N × 5.95 ^a
California (California seed)	9.4 a
Italy (California seed)	7.4 d
Spain (Spanish seed)	7.9 b
Italy (Spanish seed)	7.6 c

^a Values with different letters are statistically different at $P < 0.05$.

Milling recovery as influenced by different types of rice mills

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Machinery in milling affects the outturn of head rice and total rice. Using outmoded mills results in relatively higher quantitative and qualitative losses.

We compared different types of rice mills—steel huller (Engelberg type), disc sheller (under-runner type), and modern rubber roller mill—to assess quantitative losses. Test varieties were KS282 (medium grain) and Basmati 385 (fine grain).

samples when acetic acid extracts were analyzed by aluminum lactate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (AL-PAGE) in 10% acrylamide gel.

Overall band intensity of the Italian samples (lanes II and IV in figure) was weaker than that of American and Spanish samples (lanes I and III). Patterns of Italian samples lacked one prominent band (a in figure). The patterns

of the American and Spanish samples were nearly the same; those of the Italian samples were identical.

Differences in the electrophoregrams may be related to the differences in cooking quality. Samples of a cultivar from different agroclimatic regions should be treated separately to maintain the uniqueness of a particular germplasm and/or quality characteristics. □

Effect of rice mills on milling recovery.^a

Mill type	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)
<i>KS282</i>			
Steel huller	67.6 c	51.8 c	15.8 c
Disc sheller	70.0 b	56.2 b	13.8 b
Modern rubber roller	71.7 a	59.6 a	12.1 a
<i>Basmati 385</i>			
Steel huller	66.3 c	49.7 c	16.6 c
Disc sheller	69.0 b	54.0 b	15.0 b
Modern rubber roller	70.0 a	57.0 a	13.5 a

^a On a rough rice basis. Values with different letters are statistically different at $P < 0.05$ by DMRT.

The modern mill produced more head rice in the test varieties than did either the disc sheller or the steel huller (see table). Total milled rice percentage was also

higher with the modern mill. Different mills produced broken rice ranging from 12.1 to 15.8% for KS282 and 13.5 to 16.6% for Basmati 385. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Inheritance of resistance to rice stripe virus (RSV) in Yunnan Province, China

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We studied the inheritance of resistance to RSV in resistant foreign varieties Zhongguo 91, Fengfeng, and Tetep and native Chinese varieties Shuangfeng 1, Huxuan 19, and 683 Nuo.

Crosses were made in the fall of 1987. Parents, F_1 , and F_2 were inoculated at the three-leaf stage with viruliferous small brown planthoppers during summer 1988.

Diseased plants and heart-withered shoots were counted after 25 d. Disease-free seedlings were planted in a field of a heavily diseased district,

Results at seedling and tillering stages were analyzed using a disease index where 0–29% was considered

resistant (R), 30–59% was moderately resistant (MR), and more than 60% was infected (S).

Zhongguo 91, Fengfeng, and Tetep were highly resistant to RSV; Huxuan 19, Shuangfeng 1, and 683 Nuo were moderately resistant. Resistance was

Table 1. Resistance to RSV of parents and F_1 . Yunnan Province, China, 1988.

Parents and F_1	Plants (no.)	Disease incidence (%)	Disease index (%)	Resistance
Zhongguo 91	174	6.9	6.1	R
Huxuan 19	182	40.1	31.9	MR
Shuangfeng 1	60	58.3	51.3	MR
Fengfeng	220	18.6	16.1	R
683 Nuo	190	56.8	48.0	MR
Tetep	96	14.6	10.8	R
Zhongguo 91/Huxuan 19	11	9.1	9.1	R
Huxuan 19/Zhongguo 91	18	5.6	5.6	R
Zhongguo 91/Shuangfeng 1	10	30.0	26.7	R
683 Nuo/Fengfeng	10	20.0	10.0	R
Huxuan 19/Fengfeng	19	26.3	26.3	R
Shuangfeng 1/Tetep	19	21.1	20.2	R